

KABALA COSTAIN RESIDENTS AND WASTE DISPOSAL: AWARENESS, ATTITUDE AND WASTE DISPOSAL PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

The management of waste is a major public health problem. Developing countries have waste disposal problems which appear to differ from those found in developed countries. The main objective of this study was to determine the awareness, attitudes and waste disposal practices of Kabala Costain residents, Kaduna North Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted in this study. Simple random sampling was used to select 396 respondents from ten clusters of households. A validated questionnaire was used for data collection. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated and tested. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics and correlation which were fixed at 0.05 significant level. The result revealed that the level of awareness, attitudes and waste disposal practices of the respondents had a mean score of 9.11, 23.74, and 22.35 respectively. Almost all the respondents were aware that proper waste disposal would result in a clean environment, about 65.6% respondents strongly disagreed that attitudes had influence on the environment, and 27.7% agreed that attitudes influenced their environment. About 62.4% respondents disposed waste at any open space while 31.6% disposed their waste at the prescribed dumpsite. The study concluded that the level of awareness did not influence proper waste disposal practices but attitudinal disposition had an influence on waste disposal practices. It was therefore recommended that waste management agencies should motivate the residents to properly dispose of their waste by providing receptacles near the households and also ensure prompt waste collection services.

Keywords: Attitude, Awareness, Environment, Practices Waste disposal

INTRODUCTION

Ethically, the beauty of any environment lies on its good sanitary condition. However, there are several reports that improper waste disposal is a major challenge facing urban administrators and environmental organizations. The unsanitary conditions of collecting, processing and disposal of solid waste contribute immensely to urban environmental degradation and those found on drains obstruct waterways leading to flood which destroys lives and property and displaces people (Addaney & Anarfiwaah, 2015, Amuda et al., 2014, Butu & Mshelia, 2014).

Kaduna Environmental Protection Authority (KEPA) was established to ensure a clean and safe environment. Despite government efforts, people are carefree and still dump waste at places they find convenient to them like open space, major streets and watercourses have been converted into waste dumps sites by dwellers. These actions have led to harmful effect to the environment. Flooding is one of the major public health challenges experienced in Kabala

Costain, Kaduna North Local Government Area. Huge impacts such as loss of lives, properties and homelessness have been reported in flooded areas. To this effect, this study investigated the awareness, attitudes and waste disposal practices of Kabala Costain residents, Kaduna North Local Government, Kaduna state, Nigeria.

The management of waste is a major public health problem. Developing countries had waste disposal issues that appeared to differ from those found in developed countries especially in the areas of composition, waste amount, access to waste collection, awareness, attitudes, practices and political framework (Olukanni & Mnenga, 2015). Waste disposal in developing countries is still largely random and uncontrolled, which lead to problems associated with ineffective waste collection and disposal (Joel, Mark & Grace, 2012). Most communities in developing countries often turn to waste disposal methods that had proven to be destructive to human health and the environment like open dumping and burning (Al-Khatib, Kontogianni, Abu Nabaa, Alshami & Al-Sari', 2015; Hilburn, 2015).

Globally, indiscriminate solid waste disposal is one of the most challenging environmental problems (Allen & Basse, 2012). Waste management had attained highest importance in this era globally but the practices of basic concepts on waste disposal were often neglected. Waste disposal practice was an important factor affecting the quality of the environment. One of the causes of environmental degradation is improper solid waste disposal (Vivek, Licy, Saritha, Anies & Josphina, 2013). It was a major cause of pollution and outbreak of diseases in many parts of the world. Studies have shown that there were direct connection between human health and waste disposal, most community ailments and diseases are attributed to the quality of environment man lives. Disease conditions like malaria, diarrhea, dysentery, typhoid, cholera among others were seen as being caused by the environmental conditions where man finds himself (Mazhindu, Trynos & Tendayi, 2010). Since wholistic health was advocated by World Health Organization (WHO), hygienic method of waste disposal is very important in addressing physical, biological, chemical and socio-cultural factors in the environment that may adversely impact on the health status (Prabu, 2009). The environment plays a defining role, it is the source of global economy that ought to be managed and sustained to ensure existence. The disposal of solid waste can be costly and environmentally destructive. The environment has been on the receiving end and overburdened with aftermath of the excesses of human activities. Among all the wastes (solid, liquid and gas), solid waste was the most popular and most difficult to manage locally. This was due to the fact that solid waste did not flow, evaporate, diffuse, dissolve or be absorbed into the surrounding in contrast to liquid and gaseous wastes (Victor & Choji, 2006). Proper waste disposal was of importance because waste grows in volume and has high potential for land, water and air pollution, and was also costly to manage.

Enete (2010) defined waste as leftovers, used products whether liquid or solid having no economic value or demand and which need to be disposed or thrown away. For this study, waste is any solid or semi-solid substances which have been discarded by its primary owner or unique user, and may or may not be determined beneficial by any other person but constitute nuisance to people's health and the environment when left untreated. Waste disposal comprises

of activities like the collection, processing and deposition of unwanted solid waste materials or substances in a way that best addresses the range of public health and other environmental concerns. Disposal processes includes land filling, incineration, composting, shredding (Adogu, Uwakwe, Egenti, Okwuoha & Nkwocha, 2015).

The eight targets of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) by the United Nations are aimed at reducing poverty and improving quality of lives in developing countries. Implementation of MDGs started in 2000 to terminate in 2015. In contrast, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) contain 17 targets meant for the whole world, to be funded by the developed countries and supported by developing countries. The targets were designed to reduce poverty, promote equal opportunities and improve quality of human lives worldwide. Implementation commenced in 2016 and will terminate in 2030. A common factor in MDGs and SDGs is environmental sustainability. Though portable water and sanitation are included in the MDGs, SDGs expanded the scope to include integrated sustainable waste management strategies. These are to reduce, reuse and recycle (3 Rs).

Environmental Policies In Nigeria

The environmental policy in Nigeria was contained in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Pursuant to Section 20 of the Constitution, the state was empowered to protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air, land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria. Federal Environmental Protection Agency aim was to achieve at least 80% effective management of the municipal solid waste generated at all levels (Wilson, 2009). However, in view of the Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act, each State and local government in the country was empowered to set up its own environmental protection body and made laws to protect and improve the environment within the State.

In Kaduna State, the study location, Kaduna Environmental Protection Agency (KEPA) controls the waste generated in the State. The policy on waste management was a collaborative effort of Federal, State, Local government, private and public sectors. Federal Government of Nigeria Policy Objectives includes:

- a. Secure quality environment for all Nigerians for their health and well-being;
- b. Raise public awareness and promote understanding of the importance of relation between environment and development;
- c. To encourage individual and community participation in environmental protection and improvement efforts.

Nigeria and the Management of Municipal Solid Waste

In Nigeria, the legal framework for the management of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) was the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) now the Federal Ministry of Environment legislations. The concept of waste management was not well defined particularly in terms of type, quantities, spatial variation, administration methods, and environmental impacts. The organization charged with the responsibility of waste management in Kaduna is the State Ministry of Environment in conjunction with Kaduna Environmental Protection Authority

(KEPA). The quantity of municipal solid waste generated in Kaduna was 0.58 Kg/capita/day and 114, 433 tons monthly (Ogwueleka, 2009). Waste collection, transportation and disposal were the duty of contractors appointed by Kaduna State Government. Currently Kaduna state government spend millions yearly on services of waste contractors (Hyuwa, 2010). The Government of Kaduna State had adopted special methods of solid waste disposal. Previously, incinerators/burning had been used and presently solid waste compactors and dump sites are in use, but solid waste still constituted an important health hazard in the metropolis. Although government provide waste receptacles in some areas however people disposed waste indiscriminately. In high populated low income areas of Kawo, UngwanShanu, UngwanKanawa, Doka, TudunNupawa, HayinBanki and UngwanRimi, households resort to self-disposal services that dump waste into public drains, in streams and on bridges. Storm water flushes these solid wastes into local drains, channels and rivers contaminating sensitive ecosystems and flood plains.

Rapid urbanisation had made many waste disposal sites to be converted to settlements and housing estates (Amuda, Adebisi, Jimoda & Alade, 2014; Singh, 2011). Certain solid waste disposal practices amplify the risk level thereby exposing humans to exceptional risks which promote environmental vulnerability. Comprehending the link between solid waste disposal practices and the environment was indispensable in order to consider the contributions of the practices to increased negative environmental issues. Accumulated debris and waste on the streets which is then washed into the drainage system can result to flood. The situation is in line with the aim of this research which reviews the environmental implications of some waste disposal practices. Kabala Costain, the proposed study area had continued to witness an increase in the disposal of household waste indiscriminately on the road sides, drains and bank of the streams. Indiscriminate waste disposal, besides posing severe environmental health risk on human populations, it was also capable of inflicting everlasting damage on the ecological systems like the frequent flood being witness at Kabala Costain, the study location, which has displaced people from their homes.

Considering, the magnitude of waste released daily into the surroundings, and the reality that there appears to be no serious prepared programme for environmental friendly waste disposal method, there was need for people to be aware of the implications of their actions on the environment. A number of reviews indicated that wastes not managed appropriately could lead to water pollution which brings about diseases like cholera and typhoid (Jerry, 2015). Leakage from waste dumps often contaminate underground and surface water. Adogu et al., (2015) stated that proper waste disposal was necessary to prevent the spread of gastrointestinal and parasitic diseases caused by vectors.

The goals of municipal waste management were to promote the quality of the environment. In the process of waste management, disposal completed the waste management chronological cycle. Common methods of waste disposal in developing countries were observed to be open dumping, burying and burning of waste in open spaces, landfill, recycling and composting (Arukwe, 2012; Wilson, Araba, Chinwah & Cheeseman, 2009).

The environmental, social and health implication of indiscriminate waste disposal in many Nigeria towns and cities cannot be forgotten due to environmental abuse. Promotion of a wholesome environment is the duty of individuals, communities, agencies and the authorities. People would only promote healthy environment if they were aware of the benefits. Improvement of environmental quality depends on the manner individuals and community perceive themselves in respective to their environment. People would treat the environment, based on their personal values (Adogu et al., 2015). Adeyemo and Gboyesola (2013), Banga (2013) stated that ignorance, lack of awareness and poverty were some of the key elements that influence people's behaviour, attitudes and practices towards the environment.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of Kabala Costain residents towards waste disposal?
2. What are the attitudes of Kabala Costain residents towards waste disposal?
3. What are the practices of Kabala Costain residents towards waste disposal?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Population

A cross-sectional survey design was adopted in this study. The design enabled the testing of the statistical hypotheses and gave explanations by examining the statistical association of variables gathered during the survey. It addressed the research questions and the research objectives. The study population were residents of Kabala Costain, Kaduna North Local Government area, Kaduna State.

Sample size and sampling Technique

The sample size used for this study was determined according to Cochran's formula (1963):

$$N = \frac{Z\alpha P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

$Z\alpha^2$ = Standard normal deviate at 95% confidence interval 1.96

P = estimated prevalence (50%)

d^2 = Margin of error at 0.05

$$N = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.5(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

The minimum sample size was 381.46 respondents

10% of this sample size was added to the minimum sample size to take care of attrition

10% of 381.46 = 38.15 + 381.46 = 419.61

Approximately 420 households were employed for the study.

Cluster sampling was used because the houses were densely populated with clear outlines of distinct clusters of households. The clusters of households were numbered and randomly selected, using simple random sampling to identify the clusters to be used for the study.

Instrumentation

The research made use of self- designed questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. Sections A: contains demographic data such as gender, age, educational level, marital status and occupation. Section B: measured the awareness of towards waste disposal. It consists of 10 items with two point response format (Yes and No). The variable was measured on a 10-point rating scale. Section C: measured the attitudes towards waste disposal. It consists of 10 items on a likert five-point scale (0-4) ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Section D: measured the practices of the residents towards waste disposal. The section consists of 10 items on a likert five-point scale (0-4) ranging from Always to Never. The variable was measured on a 40-point rating scale.

Statistical Analysis: Data obtained from completed instruments were computed and analysed using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 22.0. Data were summarised by means of descriptive statistics including the frequency table, means and standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The demographic characteristics of the respondents showed that a greater number 124 (31.3%) were between ages 26 and 33 years, ages 18 to 25 were 108 (27.6%) while ages 50 and above were 22 (6%). More than half of the study population were male 232 (58.6%) compared to female respondents 164 (41.4%). Majority 258 (65.2%) of the respondents had attained a tertiary education followed by percentage below first quartile 90 (22.7%) having secondary education, with primary at 14 (3.50%) and no education at 34 (8.69%). Similarly, the married among the respondents were 197 (49.7%) compared to the singles at 174 (44%) while a small fraction of the respondents were widowed 25 (6.30%). On employment status, the self-employed were more 144 (36.6%) compared to students 120 (30.3%), and civil servants at 93 (23.5%).

Table 1: Awareness of Waste Disposal among the residents of Kabala Costain

Statements	Respondents N=396			
	Yes		No	
	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)
Awareness of proper waste disposal results to a clean environment?	392	99.0	4	1.00
Many diseases can be prevented if I dispose my waste properly?	389	98.2	7	1.80
Proper waste disposal can lead to spread of diseases like cholera, typhoid, malaria, diahorrea?	140	35.4	256	64.6
improper waste disposal can produce odour and can lead to respiratory diseases	381	96.2	15	3.80
water flowing slowly from waste dumping sites can contaminate sources of water	378	95.5	18	4.50
indiscriminate solid waste disposal into the drain system can lead to flooding	382	96.5	14	3.50
improper waste disposal has effect on the environment	387	97.7	9	2.30
I am aware that proper waste disposal can affect my health	384	97.0	12	3.0
Proper waste disposal promotes good health and enhances the environment	385	97.2	11	2.80
It is good to maintain a sanitary dustbin at home for proper waste disposal	388	98.0	8	2.00
Weighted mean (%) = 9.11 ± 0.93 (91.1)				

The awareness of respondents on waste disposal revealed that majority 392 (99%) were aware that proper waste disposal that would result to a clean environment 389 (98.2%) believed that many diseases could be prevented with having clean environment, and in contrast, more than half 256 (64.6%) of the respondents did not consider improper waste disposal to result to spread of diseases like malaria.

Majority 381 (96.2%) agreed that improper waste disposal could produce odour and lead to respiratory diseases, 378 (95.5%) agreed that water flowing slowly from waste dumpsite could contaminate sources of drinking water, 382 (96.5%) believed that indiscriminate solid waste disposal into drain system could lead to flooding. Also, 387 (97.7%) said improper waste disposal had an effect on the environment, 384 (97.0%) consented that improper waste disposal had negative impact on health, 385 (97.2%) were aware that proper waste disposal could enhance the quality of air in the environment, and 388 (98%) agreed that sanitary dustbin at home was necessary for proper waste disposal.

The awareness of respondents on waste disposal indicated that the study population had good awareness on waste disposal (mean score of 9.11 ± 0.93). Jatau (2013) stated that level of awareness should influence attitudes and waste disposal practices in a defined population, however, the findings in this study indicated that there is no relationship between awareness and waste disposal practices. A study by Adeyemo and Gboyesola (2013), found that people were more aware of traditional methods (open dumping, open burning) of waste disposal but they were ignorant of the modern methods (incineration and recycling). The findings by Momodu, Dimuna and Dimuna (2011) indicated that being aware of the consequences of improper waste disposal did no guarantee appropriate waste disposal practices which is similar with the findings of this study.

Table 2: Attitudinal Disposition of Kabala Costain Residents to Waste Disposal

Statements	SA n (%)	A n (%)	U n (%)	D n (%)	SD n (%)
My attitude to waste disposal has no influence on the environment	202(51.0)	58(14.6)	27(6.8)	75(18.9)	34(8.8)
I feel improper waste disposal is a threat to the environment	195(49.2)	160(40.4)	13(3.3)	17(4.3)	11(2.8)
I feel the use of waste bags is a way to properly dispose waste	63(15.9)	232(58.6)	75(18.9)	11(2.8)	15(3.8)
Proper separation of waste before disposal has nothing to do with waste management	53(13.4)	64(16.2)	67(16.9)	131(33.1)	81(20.5)
I feel household waste bins should be emptied often	172(43.4)	144(36.4)	29(7.3)	21(5.3)	30(7.6)
Disposing waste at any open space is also a form of proper waste disposal	130(32.8)	114(28.8)	47(11.8)	71(17.9)	34(8.6)
I do not have a role to play in proper waste disposal	136(36.3)	115(29.0)	42(10.6)	61(15.4)	42(10.6)
Proper waste disposal is solely the responsibility of the government	130(32.8)	104(26.3)	64(16.2)	60(15.2)	38(9.6)
I do not think public enlightenment will improve waste disposal	109(27.6)	114(28.8)	40(10.1)	42(10.6)	91(23.0)
My low income earning prevents me from engaging the waste collectors to dispose my waste	60(15.2)	42(10.6)	89(22.5)	125(31.6)	80(20.2)
Weighted mean (%) = 23.74 ± 5.18 (59.4)					

The attitudinal disposition of respondents indicated that majority 260 (65.6%) of the respondents strongly believed that their attitudes did not have any influence on the environment, 355 (89.6%) considered improper waste disposal as a threat to the environment and the use of waste bags to dispose waste had become a norm for most 295 (74.5%) of the respondents. About half (50.6%) of the respondents felt that proper separation of waste before disposal was inappropriate, 316 (79.8%) supported the idea that household bins should be emptied on a daily basis, more than half (61.6%) of the respondents considered any open space ideal for waste disposal. Similarly, 251 (63.3%) of the respondents did not think of themselves as having any role in waste disposal, 234 (59.1%) believed that waste disposal was the sole responsibility of the government, 223 (56.4%) believed that no public enlightenment could change the situation of things, while 205 (51.8%) did not hold to their low income as their reason for improper waste disposal.

Following a high level of awareness recorded in this study, the attitudinal disposition of respondents indicated an moderate performance (23.74 ± 5.18) which was similar to the findings of Alem (2007). Johnston (2010) found out that for attitude to improve persuasive communications and information were necessary to influence attitude. The majority of the study population strongly believed that their attitudes had no influence on the environment, while some believed that their attitudes could influence their environment. This indicated that people would treat the environment based on their personal values which was similar to the findings of Adogu et al., (2015) which stated that people would keep a clean environment if they felt a clean environment was essential for human existence. Separation (reuse and recycling) of waste before disposal was believed to be inappropriate which was consistent with the findings of Momodu, Dimuna and Dimuna (2011) that stated that high awareness of benefits of recycling did not imply positive attitudes and proper waste disposal practices like recycling. Also, a good awareness level should have amounted to a high attitudinal disposition, however, majority of the respondents considered open waste dumping appropriate. They did not believe that public enlightenment could change the situation of things with regards to proper waste disposal practices. The negative view on waste disposal were the major reasons why people had carefree attitudes towards proper waste disposal (Gondo, 2010; Chekole, 2006) hence, this explained the average level of attitudes among the study population.

Table 3: Waste Disposal Practices of Kabala Costain Resident

Statements	A n (%)	O n (%)	U n (%)	R n (%)	N n (%)
I only dispose waste at designated collections points or dumpsites	241(60.9)	96(24.2)	8(2.0)	42(10.6)	9(2.3)
Dumpsite is far away so I dispose waste at any open space	192(48.5)	55(13.9)	24(6.1)	80(20.2)	45(11.4)
I dispose my waste in drainages	238(60.1)	35(8.8)	50(12.6)	42(10.6)	31(7.8)
I openly burn my waste	98(25.0)	83(21.0)	43(10.9)	86(21.7)	85(21.5)
I separate my waste to remove reuse able materials like bottles, cans before disposing it	61(15.5)	75(18.9)	78(19.7)	101(25.5)	81(20.5)
I dispose waste directly to waste collectors	50(12.6)	87(22.0)	58(14.6)	112(28.3)	89(22.5)
I dump my waste at the backyard	193(48.7)	46(11.6)	51(12.9)	55(13.9)	51(12.9)
I bury household waste under the ground	20(5.1)	45(11.4)	65(16.4)	28(7.1)	238(60.1)
I bury kitchen waste then use it for manure	16(4.0)	30(7.6)	61(15.4)	54(13.6)	235(59.3)
I dispose my waste in nearby rivers because water can flush it away	263(66.4)	44(11.1)	39(9.8)	26(6.6)	24(6.1)
Weighted mean (%) = 22.35 ± 4.38 (55.9)					

On waste disposal practices, the study results revealed that 337 (85.1%) of the respondents disposed waste at designated collection points or dumpsites, 245 (62.4%) disposed their waste at any open space because dumpsite is far away, 273 (68.9%) disposed waste in drainages, 181 (46%) practiced open burning, and 137 (34.6%) respondents separated waste. Among respondents whose waste were been collected by waste collectors were 137 (34.6%) against 201 (50.8%) of respondents who did not dispose their waste through waste collectors and 58 (14.6%) being indifferent. Majority 239 (60.3%) of the respondents disposed their waste at their backyard (open field). Similarly, burying household waste underground was reported among the respondents at 65 (16.5%), 46 (11.6%) buried waste and used it for manure, while 307 (77.5%) of the respondents disposed their waste into the river.

Waste disposal practices as observed in this study revealed that majority of the respondents still practice the traditional waste disposal methods. Majority of the study population disposed their waste anywhere. According to Addaney and Anarfiwaah (2015), Butu and Mshelia (2014) waste dumped in drainages often block the drainages and could result in flooding. From the findings of this study, majority of the respondents dumped their waste in drainages which explained the reason for the frequent flood experienced at Kabala Costain. Majority of the respondents disposed their waste at the backyard (open field) or into the river. The result of this study with regards to open burning and open dumps as the commonest methods of waste disposal is consistent with findings by Onwughara, Nnorom and Kanno (2010); Nabegu (2010). Banga (2013) reported in her work that participation in proper waste disposal practices depended on the level of awareness, educational level and gender but that was not consistent with the findings of this research as there were no significant relationship between demographic variables with the waste disposal practices likewise, there was no significant relationship between awareness and waste disposal practices but there was significant relationship between attitudes and waste disposal practices. This indicated that, aside awareness and attitudes to waste disposal, there might be other factors that hindered proper waste disposal practices like commitment to waste collection.

Conclusion

The study revealed the true nature of waste disposal practices of Kabala Costain residents, Kaduna State, a high level of awareness among respondents were observed with a moderate attitudes and waste disposal practices among respondents. Level of awareness did not influence proper waste disposal practices but attitudinal disposition had an influence on waste disposal practices. Hence, a continuous supportive waste management system and health education on proper waste disposal practices needs to be addressed in Kabala Costain, Kaduna State.

Recommendations

Strict supervision and surveillance of waste disposal activities is recommended. To achieve the goal of safe waste disposal practices in household, awareness, education on importance of safe waste disposal program should be initiated for the public. Laws should be publicized on safe waste disposal methods; this should be adequately promoted and advertised. Government should encourage private/government partnership in wastes management at an affordable rate. It is very important that the related professionals such as the environmental inspectors become involved as they play a vital role in promoting proper waste disposal. Waste disposal laws either by local government or Ministry of Environment should ensure that safe waste disposal practices were embarked upon and waste should not be discarded in the rivers, gutters, drains, open space or public locations like buildings or streets. Waste management agency should ensure prompt collection of waste and also provide waste receptacles closer to households in order to motivate residents to dispose waste properly at designated dumpsites.

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